

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

repeat_region: MtrunA17_Chr3R0310480;

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Supplementary Dataset S26. Expression profiles of ten non-overlapping repeat elements that have log₂ TMM values above zero. Screenshots are from the RNA-Seq-based gene expression atlas of *Medicago truncatula* (MtExpress v. 3, <https://medicago.toulouse.inrae.fr/GEA>). The list corresponds to repeat elements marked with “Yes” in column B of Supplementary Dataset S25. For clarity and better visibility, only the core sample set is shown. Note that some repeat elements in this list have tissue- or sample-specific expression.